

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Using the Standalone Registration User Interface

How to register tissue blocks into 3D reference organs using the stand-alone Registration User Interface

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Introduction

The Human Reference Atlas (<https://humanatlas.io>) supports the spatial and semantic registration of healthy human tissue blocks from a variety of curated sources into a 3D common coordinate framework. This SOP focuses on registering tissue blocks from sources without an integrated interface. It contains instructions for using the standalone Registration User Interface (RUI) (<https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui/>). The primary goal is to facilitate an accurate and efficient tissue registration process. The latest video demonstration of this process can be found at https://youtu.be/j4f9_xdBrK0.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **RUI Support Personnel** are members of the Indiana University team who assist users with tissue registrations.

The **Tissue Data Provider** is the person utilizing the RUI to register tissue blocks.

Role	Name	Email
RUI Support Personnel	Andreas Bueckle Danial Qaurooni	abueckle@iu.edu , dequeue@iu.edu
Tissue Data Provider	various	various

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

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Procedures

Preparing for registration

- Make sure the RUI supports your organ by visiting the latest HRA organ library available at: <https://humanatlas.io/3d-reference-library>. As of September 2024, the RUI supports 65 healthy human adult organs.
- Gather any materials needed to document where the tissue block was extracted from. At a minimum, this includes donor sex, tissue organ, and approximate tissue size.
 - Note: If you are missing metadata needed for spatial registration, please refer to the Tissue Registration Issues section below. Except in rare circumstances, we encourage you to proceed with registration and document the missing information.
- Navigate to the Registration User Interface at: <https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui>

Acquiring extraction site

The user approaches the standalone RUI to either reuse an existing extraction site that has been previously created for a different tissue sample or create a new extraction site from scratch.

Creating a new extraction site

Enter metadata

- When opening the standalone RUI, you are presented with a small window, see **Fig. 1**. You need to enter the required data before you can start the registration process.

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Start Registration

Author Data

First Name * Middle Name Last Name *

ORCID identifier (optional)

Donor Data

Donor Sex: Male Female

Select an organ:

Upload previous registration data (optional):

Upload

No file(s) uploaded

Continue

Figure 1. Metadata input window for the RUI.

- Author Data
 - Enter your name and optional ORCID into the corresponding text entry fields.
- Donor Data
 - Select the donor's sex.
 - Select an organ from the drop-down menu. Make sure to select the right or left version as appropriate. The organ might take a few seconds to load.

Click OK to complete this step and enter the RUI space.

Place tissue

If this is your first time using the RUI, please read through the Description of the User Interface (UI) section, which is included as an appendix to this document.

- Resize the tissue block using the Tissue Block Dimensions text input fields in the top right corner. The default is a 10x10x10 mm block.
- Enter tissue section thickness in micrometers.
- Move the tissue block into position.
- When using the mouse, the tissue block can only be moved in two dimensions at a time.

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- To make “looking inside” the reference organ easier, all anatomical structures are set to 20% opacity as the default. You can adjust the opacity using the Anatomical Structures accordion menu in the metadata pane.
- To inspect tissue blocks you placed before (for reference), click the Previously Registered Blocks toggle button in the metadata pane on the left. Clicking this toggle button will show all previously registered tissue blocks based on your browser’s local cache. This feature is supported on all major browsers.
- To change the perspective, use the radio buttons in the 3D pane.
- To verify the placement, switch to 3D Preview mode using the corresponding toggle switch at the top of the 3D pane.
- At any time, the tissue block can be moved by pressing the W, A, S, D, Q, or E keyboard buttons, see **Fig. 2**. Each button moves the tissue block by 0.5 mm either into the positive or negative direction of an axis. The WASDQE buttons can be used at any time, regardless of whether the application is in Register or 3D Preview mode.

Figure 2: The WASDQE buttons move the tissue block along individual axes.

- Adjust the rotation of the tissue block by using the rotation sliders in the manipulation pane on the right.

Review and download registration data

- Once you have entered all the location, donor, sample, and author data:
 - Click the Review and Download button in the bottom right corner of the screen to review the data and download it as a JSON file.

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- A Registration Review window pops up so you can check the validity of the data you generated.
 - Download the JSON file to your hard drive. You can then share the registration data with the RUI Support Person listed in the Roles and Responsibilities section above, who will work with you to facilitate its downstream usage.

After completing the registration process, download the RUI data in JSON format and share it with the Indiana University team. The RUI data will then be made available via the public Exploration User Interface (EUI) (<https://apps.humanatlas.io/eui/>) for validating accuracy.

Reusing an existing extraction site

- To modify and/or reuse an existing extraction site, you need to have the relevant JSON file ready. After opening the RUI, go to the modal window (**Fig. 1**), select Upload, and navigate to the folder where the JSON is located.
- Make any adjustments to the location and metadata of the extraction site.
- Once completed, click the Review and Download button in the bottom right corner of the screen to review the data and download it as a JSON file.

Validating registration

It is important to verify the registration before making it public. The RUI Support Person listed above will provide you with a custom EUI link for this purpose. A video demonstration of this validation process is available via the following link: <https://youtu.be/UloDIG0S64w>.

Verification involves checking the following details for accuracy:

- Demographic information, such as sex, age, and BMI
- Tissue block information, including the 3D size, position, and rotation of the tissue blocks. If tissue blocks were cut into sections, make sure to verify their number, thickness, and sequence using the listing on the right hand side (see **Fig. 4**).
- Technology information, including assay types (e.g., CODEX) or suspensions (e.g., scRNAseq analysis). Make sure all data is available for each tissue section or suspension on the right hand side.

After verifying the details above, you can inform the RUI Support Person to let them know of any discrepancies or confirm accuracy.

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Figure 3: The Exploration User Interface (EUI).

Figure 4: One tissue block with tissue sections and their associated datasets.

Tissue Registration Issues

The Tissue Provider might have doubts about whether the tissue sample can or should be spatially registered. For example, the tissue might be missing some metadata or there might be a mismatch between tissue sample size and 3D reference size. With a few exceptions, the general guidance in such cases is to proceed with the registration process while documenting the issue.

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- Please document registration issues using the following Google Form:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe0falih0S-1zqn5FCdalCF7YTxK7ECMgg0svVv0dvIEF7gKQ/viewform>.
- Based on the nature of your issue, you will either be granted an exemption from registration or asked to document the caveat and proceed.

Best Practices

Below is a list of best practices to ensure that the spatial registration process goes smoothly and the likelihood of errors is minimized:

Complete spatial registration when tissues are sectioned

Prioritize conducting spatial registrations directly after sectioning tissue samples whenever possible. This approach helps preserve the accuracy of spatial information and minimizes morphological alterations that might occur over time.

Document the extraction site in detail

In scenarios where immediate spatial registration is impractical, carefully document the extraction site. Photographs and detailed annotations on anatomical images can help accurately capture the original location and orientation of the tissue. Such documentation can aid subsequent registration efforts.

Preserve context

- For diseased tissue, clinical imaging, surgeon's operative notes (if available), and pathology notes can provide insights into the specific characteristics and conditions of the tissue.
- For normal tissue, communication between the surgeon, the tissue collector, and the specimen collection manager can improve documentation accuracy and handling of tissue samples.

Use anatomical landmarks to align tissue

The Anatomical Landmarks pane on the bottom left side of the RUI interface serves as a useful reference for orienting tissue samples and navigating reference organs.

Train multiple team members to use the RUI

Ensure that multiple team members are trained in using the RUI to prevent processing bottlenecks. Having several proficient RUI users allows for continuity in work, even in the absence of key personnel.

References and Resources

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- Standalone Registration User Interface (RUI): <https://apps.humanatlas.io/eui>. Accessed on May 23, 2024.
- HuBMAP Exploration User Interface (EUI): <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>
- SenNet Exploration User Interface (EUI): <https://data.sennetconsortium.org/ccf-eui>
- RUI Demo (v3.8.0): https://youtu.be/j4f9_xdBrK0. Accessed on Nov 13, 2024.
- HRA Portal: <https://humanatlas.io>. Accessed on May 23, 2024.
- Validation demo: <https://youtu.be/UloDIG0S64w>. Accessed on Nov 13, 2024.

Glossary

Cellular Senescence Network (SenNet): The Cellular Senescence Network was established and funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health to comprehensively identify and characterize the differences in aging cells across the body, across various states of human health, and across the lifespan. SenNet will provide publicly accessible atlases of senescence using data collected from multiple human and mouse tissues.

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health. HuBMAP is developing the tools to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be used to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

Mapping Component-Indiana University (MC-IU): The Indiana University team is one of two teams in the HuBMAP consortium tasked with building an atlas of tissue maps. These two teams are identified as mapping components, as opposed to components or teams that develop tools or provide infrastructure support.

Reference Organ: A reference organ is a 3D model based on a variety of potential data sources produced by MC-IU. Subject matter experts are involved with the creation of 3D models.

Registration User Interface (RUI): Registration user interface developed by MC-IU, available via the HuBMAP Data Ingest Portal and <https://apps.humanatlas.io/rui>.

Tissue Block: A tissue block is a digital, 3D representation of a tissue sample. In the RUI, tissue blocks are cuboids that the user can spatially register to a reference organ.

Tissue Section: A tissue section is a slice of a tissue block. Tissue sections inherit the location and rotation of their parent tissue block. The thickness and number of tissue sections is captured with an input field inside the RUI.

Tissue Suspension: A tissue prepared for bulk analysis.

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Appendix: Description of the Registration User Interface (RUI)

The RUI currently supports tissue registration for the organs listed in the 3D Reference Object Library, which can be found at <https://humanatlas.io/3d-reference-library>.

Figure 1: The stand-alone RUI. The yellow cuboid represents the tissue block. The green slide indicates the bisection line inside the kidney.

The RUI layout consists of three panes (Fig. 2): the **structures and landmarks** pane on the left, the **3D** pane in the middle, and the **metadata and manipulation** pane on the right.

Figure 2: The RUI has three panes: anatomical structures and landmarks (left with pink outline), 3D view (middle in yellow), and tissue block metadata and manipulation (right in blue).

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The following is a brief description of the actions each pane makes possible.

- The left pane contains the following elements:
 - a. **Anatomical Structures** lists the 3D structures inside the selected reference organ. A slider appears when you hover over the drop icon to the left of the anatomical structure text entry, making it possible to adjust the opacity of the structure. This allows making certain parts of the organ more transparent than others and retaining certain structures as landmarks while omitting others to facilitate tissue placement. Clicking the eye icon to the right of the slider will hide the structure.
 - b. **Landmarks** lists visual cues that allow you to recognize the anatomy of the organ (such as the bisection line for the kidney). All landmarks are hidden by default and if made visible are rendered in green.
- The **3D pane** in the middle contains the reference organ and the tissue block. It is a 3D window, similar to what one would find in 3D modeling software or a video game. In the top left corner, a set of radio buttons allow you to control the 3D camera of the scene.
 - a. Using the radio buttons labeled Left, Right, Anterior, and Posterior, you can rotate the camera around the reference organ in increments of 90 degrees. The current camera view is visually indicated by a small human icon on the right side of the 3D pane.
 - b. When Left, Right, Anterior, or Posterior are clicked, the camera movement is restricted to 90 degree increments, and the mouse is used to move the tissue block. Select 3D Preview to verify tissue placement. When in 3D Preview mode, you can rotate the camera at two degrees of freedom while clicking and dragging the left mouse button. You can also zoom in by using the mouse scroll wheel (or whatever input method is assigned to scrolling) and pan the camera (i.e., move it laterally) by clicking and dragging the right mouse button.

Figure 3: The z-axis should correspond to the cutting direction of the tissue block.

- c. In the top right corner, the current x, y, z-coordinates of the tissue block are shown, with the origin in the back bottom left corner of the reference organ.

